

PROFILE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE, QUALITY MANAGEMENT, AND COMPETENCE OF PRINCIPALS IN SARAWAK

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the profile of emotional intelligence, quality management, and competence of principals in Sarawak. The sample used 152 principals from all types of schools. data was collected using questionnaires developed from the Malaysian Emotional Intelligence Inventory (MEQI) and Malaysian Competitiveness Standards (SKKSM). The analysis technique used is Mann Whitney U for gender and Kruskal Wallis-H for age and experience. The test results found that gender is significantly related to emotional intelligence ($z = 0.043$, $p < .05$) and competence ($z = 0.025$, $p < .05$) but does not have a significant relationship with quality management ($z = 0.200$, $p > .05$). In addition, the findings also show that different ages have a significant difference in terms of quality management ($\chi^2 = 10.072$, $p < .05$), but there is no significant difference in emotional intelligence ($\chi^2 = 6.997$, $p > .05$), and competence ($\chi^2 = 3.571$, $p > .05$). For the experience of students, the findings of the study show that different periods of experience for chi square (5, $N = 152$) do not have a significant level of difference in terms of emotional intelligence ($\chi^2 = 3.957$, $p > .05$), quality management ($\chi^2 = 2.507$, $p > .05$), and leadership competence ($\chi^2 = 2.590$, $p > .05$). In conclusion, it can be concluded that

there is a difference in the level of emotional intelligence and competence for gender, but there is no difference in quality management. In addition, different ages have different levels in terms of quality management but do not have different levels in terms of emotional intelligence and competence. Based on experience, different periods of experience do not have different levels of emotional intelligence, quality management, and leadership competence.

Keywords: *emotional intelligence, competence, quality management, principal*

A. INTRODUCTION

Schools are community institutions that have a specific purpose, which is to shape and change the behavior of students (educate) in the desired direction. In addition, schools are also mind-changers and determinants of the culture and development of a country. In powering the system education, the role of schools and educational institutions are seen as increasingly challenging and need to be competitive. (Mohd Rasidi, 2013). Behavioral changes a student is a goal to be achieved through school functions. The task of the principal is to perform this function to create an atmosphere that can cause or produce changes in behavior (Atan Long 1978). Principals are employees in a large and complex organization. Teaching and learning in the era of globalization is quite a tiring experience. The competition and challenges of this kind of work environment may have negative effects on principals and students. This can cause an emotional outburst between both parties, this scenario can affect the principal's image if it happens. Skovholt and D'Rozario's (2000) study shows that students consider empathetic and sociable principals to be excellent principals. This finding reinforces the results of Grasha's (1996) study which found that excellent principals are principals who are empathetic and attentive to the needs of students. Overall, this article intended to study emotional intelligence (EQ) profile, quality management and competence of secondary school principals based on the study of Noriah et al (2004), Oakland Quality Management theory (1996) and the Iceberg Competency Model by Hay Mcber (1993). Therefore, this discussion will answer several research questions as follows:

1. What is the profile of emotional intelligence of secondary school principals in Sarawak as a whole and comparison by gender, age and experience?

2. What is the overall quality management profile of secondary school principals in Sarawak and comparisons by gender, age and experience?
3. What is the overall competency profile of secondary school principals in Sarawak and the comparison by gender, age and experience?

B. BACKGROUND OF STUDY

The new knowledge in the field of emotional intelligence has been widely disseminated and has succeeded in raising public awareness and confidence in the concept of emotional intelligence starting after Goleman published his book on emotional intelligence titled *Emotional Intelligence* which was published in 1995. Since then, emotional intelligence has begun to be recognized for its importance and impact in a person's life, especially in matters involving interactions between people (Alegre, 2012).

In recent years, understanding the concept of emotional intelligence has received attention in society and academia. Several studies have confirmed that there is a relationship between emotional intelligence and several positive developments in human life, including well-being and mental health (Gallagher & Vella-Brodrick, 2008); strategies in making adjustments (Petrides, Furnham, & Mavroveli, 2007); mental management abilities and positive personalities (Van Roy & Viswesvaran, 2004); making adjustments in school (Adeyemo, 2005); and also physical and psychological health (Santrock, 2004). In fact, early studies have shown that emotional intelligence has been found to have a positive influence on life such as well-being (Bar-On, 2000); mental health (Bernet, 1996); efficiency at work and also in community life (Finnegan, 1998); success in life (Goleman, 1995); and also positive life outcomes (Goleman, 2001; Mayer & Solevay, 1990).

Based on this importance, starting in the 1980s, researchers in the West began to look at the importance of this emotional aspect as a basis for effectiveness in an organization (Opengart, 2003; Callahan & McCollum, 2002; Yukl, 2002). Commercial organizations have shown that emotions have played a very important role in leadership towards generating motivation and increasing subordinate commitment to the organization (Forgas, 1995; George & Brief, 1992).

An organization that is said to be of quality involves the quality aspect of all educational staff starting from school leaders to middle leaders, teachers and support staff. The quality of educational staff is related to the competence and potential of a leader of an educational organization (Institut Aminuddin Baki, 2006). In going through these developments and changes, various challenges must be faced by the Ministry of Education to ensure that goals are achieved. Based on the history of the implementation of quality management at the global level, for example in the United States, Japan, the United Kingdom and Thailand, this quality management practice is actively carried out and has been proven to have an extraordinary impact on the development of various sectors including the field of education.

C. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The excellence and effectiveness of the school depends on the combined efforts of principals and school organizations in an effort to bring about change towards excellence (Raja Maizatul, 2013). Therefore, the Malaysian education system has gone through many developments and changes to achieve the government's goal of providing quality education to the people to produce human capital that can compete in the international arena. Goleman (1995) stated that someone who does not have the ability to control emotions when interacting with others is not motivated to do their job well. They also cannot be classified as successful individuals in their respective careers. The emotional outburst events described, especially those that occur in the workplace, have implications for the level of emotional stability and maturity possessed by the individuals involved.

A research is an effort or action to address a problem faced (Lodico, Spaulding & Voegtler, 2006). The research problem refers to a situation that requires discussion, solution and further information that coincides with a study (Noraini Idris, 2010). In this study, the problem statement covers the main aspects of the study, namely demographic factors, emotional intelligence, quality management and also competence. In addition, it also discusses issues in the leadership of principals that occur in managing a school.

The emotional intelligence is linked to the issue of principal leadership. At the same time, many opinions state that the success of a school is related to the leadership of its principal (Ishak Sin, 2002; Abbas Awang & Balasandran, 2002). However, the extent to which school leaders appreciate the quality of leadership to improve the excellence of their respective schools has quality in leadership, influential, willing to sacrifice for the interests of the organization, creative in leadership, innovative, and skilled in communication are important characteristics in generating school excellence (Aminah Ayob, 2004).

D. LITERATURE REVIEW

Demographic factors are also among the factors that affect emotions, quality management, and a person's competence. Demographics in this study include gender, age, and experience. All these factors are stated in the study of Bar-On (2000), Click (2002), and Sala (2002). In relation to demographics, there are several studies that have been conducted discussing the differences in findings in the factors of gender, age, and experience of a principal.

a. Gender

In the gender factor, some research has been done to prove that gender also affects the emotional intelligence of an individual. Mayer, Caruso and Salovey (1999) stated that female administrators have an advantage compared to males in emotional intelligence. Calvallo and Brienza (2002) who conducted a study on 358 managers of Johnson and Johnson Consumer and Personal Care Group found that there was a significant difference in emotional competence based on gender.

Based on the ECI instrument, female managers obtained higher scores than male managers in competence; emotional awareness, caring, developing others, service orientation, and communication (Boyatzis and Sala, 2004). However, female managers have higher scores in the competencies of adaptability and service orientation based on the evaluation done by supervisors. Based on the overall report of this study, there is no significant difference between men and women. Boyatzis and Sala's (2004) study based on the ECI instrument found that women obtained

higher scores in the competencies of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and social skills.

In addition, Rivera (2003) conducted research on a group of Puerto Rican men and women who worked full-time or part-time who were also studying part-time in college, based on an emotion study instrument. The findings of the research show that there is a significant difference in emotional competence between male and female workers where male respondents who work obtain higher scores than females in eight aspects of competence at work compared to at home, namely; self-emotional awareness, confidence, caring, service orientation, catalyst for change, and loyalty to the organization. Nevertheless, women have obtained scores in nine aspects of competence higher than men at home than at work, namely self-confidence, reliability, adaptability, service orientation, organizational awareness, inspirational leadership, communication, conflict management, and group cooperation.

Similar findings were also shown by Imndell and Pherwani (2003) who studied gender differences related to transformational leadership style and its relationship with emotional competence among organizational managers, based on the theory of emotional competence of leaders by Goleman (1995). The results of the study show that there is a significant difference in emotional intelligence scores based on gender, where female respondents obtain higher scores in emotional competence compared to male managers. However, according to Bar-On (2000) there is no significant difference between male and female administrators in relation to the overall aspect of emotions and social competence, but he did not state some of these differences in the component factorization.

In the theory presented by Bar-On, female administrators are more careful about emotions, more empathetic, build good interpersonal relationships and care more about social relationships than male administrators. Despite this, male administrators show better self-image, less dependence, more flexibility and optimism when compared to female administrators. In general, if you look at the level of measurement between men and women, there are many similarities that exist than differences related to emotional intelligence. In other words, there is no gender difference in relation to emotional intelligence (Bar-On, 1997).

Oshagbemi (2000) in his study on gender differences with the work commitment of university lecturers in the United Kingdom showed that female lecturers have more commitment to the organization than their male counterparts. They are also more satisfied with their income than men. However, male lecturers are more satisfied with the work environment than female lecturers.

b. Age

The study of Noriah et al. (2003) who said age and experience are factors to a person's emotional intelligence, that is, the higher the age, the higher the commitment to work. In this age factor as well, several studies prove that it has an influence on emotional intelligence. The increase in a person's age can lead to the construction and improvement in the competence of emotional intelligence (Sala, 2002). This is because the maturity of a person's emotional intelligence competence is through learning and experience in life (Boyatzis & Sala, 2004).

According to Goleman (1998), a person's emotional intelligence increases with age. Bar-On (2000) found that the older group obtained a higher Emotional Quotient Inventory score than the younger group. Individuals in their late 40s and early 50s scored higher. Therefore, Bar-on (2000) concluded that emotional intelligence can increase in parallel with the increase of the person's age.

The same thing has been shown by Click (2002) who studied emotional intelligence with administrative experience among 85 students in the educational administration master's program at the University of East Tennessee. His study found that older students obtained higher aggregate scores in social skills and emotional intelligence. However, a study conducted by Cook (2006) on principals in the Montana district in the United States to see the effect of emotional intelligence on the effectiveness of principal leadership, showed that the principal's age did not have a significant effect on emotional intelligence.

c. Experience

As for the aspect of experience, a study by Click (2002) that looked at the relationship between experience based on years of service in administration with

emotional intelligence scores among students who followed the master's program in educational administration at East Tennessee University, the findings of the study showed that there was no significant relationship in between experience based on years of service with the aggregate score of emotional intelligence competence. The emotional intelligence score for students who have a year or more of experience in administration is in a moderate position while for students who have no experience in administration, the majority obtains a low emotional intelligence score (Click, 2002).

Mustamin et al. al (2013) in their study on the comparison of school principals between Malaysia and Indonesia showed that the level of competence of principals in Malaysia is generally higher than the competence of principals in Indonesia and there is also a significant difference between the competence of school principals in Malaysia and Indonesia. This aspect is related to the experience and service of a principal where it differentiates the experience of principals in Malaysia and Indonesia. In other words, different experiences will lead to different styles of leadership.

Similar to the findings in Latin America, Fernandez-Araoz (2001) conducted a study on 200 executives, to determine the level of success related to work experience and the level of emotional intelligence. He uses IQ as the basis of evaluation through the interview method. For successful executives the aspects that have a significant relationship are emotional intelligence, work experience and the third is IQ. For executives identified as failing, there is a relationship with work experience, and IQ. Most of them are weak in overall emotional intelligence.

C. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Study Design

This study is quantitative in nature by using a questionnaire that contains all important aspects to obtain selected information data. The questionnaires were personally distributed by the researcher to the respondents where the respondents were provided with a set of questionnaires that needed to be answered. A quantitative study was chosen because it involves a large group and also it is related to issues and problems. Quantitative design was chosen for this study because based on Creswell's

(2014) statement, quantitative methods are suitable for explaining the relationship between variables in the study and how a variable affects other variables as well as knowing whether a factor is an expectation of a result (Gay, Mills & Airasian, 2012). Survey methods through questionnaires are popular for non-experimental studies in various fields, especially social science studies (Chua, 2012) and education (McMillan, 2012). In addition, quantitative research was found to be suitable for this study which examines the impact of variables on a certain outcome in addition to aiming to test and explain theories that can be applied to a large population (Creswell, 2009).

Study sampling

The technique of simple random sampling (simple random sampling) was chosen because this technique is a basic technique where the researcher identifies and selects a group of subjects (sample) to be studied from a larger group (population). A total of 152 principals serving in all secondary schools in Sarawak participated in this study. All principals involved are secondary school principals who serve under the Malaysian Ministry of Education.

Research instrument

In order to carry out this study, a set of IKEM-MEQI questionnaires built by Noriah et al (2003) was used as a research instrument. This instrument consists of 95 items using a five-point Likert scale to measure all seven domains of emotional intelligence, 10 quality management principles and three competency characteristics.

According to Othman Mohamed (2001), researchers must ensure the validity and reliability of research tools to ensure the validity and reliability of the test. Therefore, the researcher has asked the supervisor to examine the content of the instrument given to the principal. Validity or validity is a concept that refers to the extent to which the research tool measures what is to be measured or the extent to which the research tool fulfills its task (Anastasi & Urbina, 1997). An instrument can be validated if the instrument gives consistent results every time the measurement is made (Noraini Idris, 2010).

The internal consistency method (internal consistency approach) Cronbach's Alpha is used in this study. In this method, items that have high reliability with test index scores have high reliability. While the items that have a low correlation value are removed from the test. If the value of $r > .60$, this means that the level of trust of the measurement tool is high (Ary et al., 2002; Chua, 2012). While a reliability coefficient that is less than $.60$, it can be considered that the analyzed instrument has a low reliability value and needs to be improved or removed to increase the coefficient.

For this study, the reliability of the research instrument was examined to ensure that the measurer evaluates the dimensions that should be measured (Sekaran, 2000). Mohd Majid Konting (1997) suggested Cronbach Alpha at a level of 0.70 and above, as an Alpha value that has high reliability. In this study, the researcher used the recommended Cronbach alpha value of 0.70 as the accepted reliability value.

Critical study

In addition, the pilot study also aims to obtain the validity and reliability of the items found in the questionnaire. Ahmad Mahzan (in A. Santha, 2002) stated that the pilot test was conducted to determine that the questions given to the respondents were appropriate and easy to understand by them. According to Mohd Najib (2003), a pilot study is an important activity for every survey study where apart from determining the validity and reliability of the instrument, it is also used to test the best method of administering the instrument, getting to know the sample and the appropriateness of the analysis method.

In this study, a pilot study was conducted on senior secondary school assistants who are running the NPQEL course at the Aminuddin Baki Institute, Kuching. The time given to respondents in this pilot study is 20 to 30 minutes to answer all the questions given in the questionnaire. A total of 50 questionnaires were distributed and 36 were returned.

The result of the pilot study for demographics is $.723$, emotional intelligence Cronbach Alpha value is $.775$ and for competence the Cronbach Alpha value is $.816$. Therefore, items that get a good Cronbach alpha value in this questionnaire can be

accepted and used for real research, which are emotional intelligence and competence items. While for the demographic items the form of the questions was changed or for the actual study because during the pilot test there was confusion about the questions given.

Data Analysis

The raw data obtained was analyzed using SPSS and SMARTPLS. For this study, statistical tests SPSS version 23.0, and SMARTPLS 3.0 were used to analyze the data. With SPSS, one of the tests used is descriptive analysis used to analyze the principal's emotional intelligence level by looking at the mean score obtained. For this study, objective 1 uses descriptive statistical analysis involving mean and standard deviation to determine the level of emotional intelligence, quality management and principal competence.

Next for objective 2, which is to identify the level of differences in emotional intelligence, quality management competence, and Mann Whitney-U and Kruskal Wallis and used to obtain data for the demographic effects of gender, age and experience. Mann Whitney-U and Kurskal Wallis tests were used to see how the influence of all variables together on the dependent variable. In this study, the Mann Whitney-U test was used to identify the level of differences in emotional intelligence, quality management and competence for gender and Kruskal Wallis was used to identify the level of difference in emotional intelligence, quality management and competence for age and experience. In this section, the independent variables used are gender, age and experience and the dependent variables measured are emotional intelligence, quality management and competence.

D. RESEARCH FINDINGS

The discussion about emotional intelligence profile, quality management and also the principal's competence based on gender, age and also experience is divided into three parts which are differences in emotional intelligence, quality management and also leadership competence. Profiles of emotional intelligence, quality management and competence of respondents among principals based on demographics were analyzed using independent T-tests for gender and one-way ANOVA for age and experience.

This is because the objective is to see the effect of variables individually for gender and also together for age and experience on the dependent variable. After the analysis was done using SPSS, the results of the study were as discussed in this section.

a. Demographic Analysis

A total of 152 respondents have been involved in this study who have various backgrounds. There are several demographic variables involved in this study including gender, age, type of school, position, experience, management training and type of training.

Table 1: Demographic distribution of respondents

No.	Demographic Variables	N	%
1	Gender		
	Men	117	77.0
	Female	35	23.0
2	Age		
	41-45 years old	38	25.0
	46-50 years old	72	47.4
	51-55 years old	39	25.7
	56-60 years old	3	2.0
3	Type of School		
	National High School	132	86.8
	National Religious High School	5	3.3
	Religious Secondary School	4	2.6
	Technical / Vocational High School	4	2.6
	School of Art	1	0.7
	Others	6	3.9
4	Division		
	Kuching	46	30.3
	Samarahan	11	7.2
	Sri Aman	5	3.3

	Betong	11	7.2
	Sarikei	8	5.3
	Serial	4	2.6
	Sibu	16	10.5
	Bntulu	6	3.9
	Miri	23	15.1
	Limba	7	4.6
	Face	7	4.6
	Capit	8	5.3
5	Grade		
	DG44	3	2.0
	DG48	4	2.6
	DG52	84	55.3
	DG54	59	38.8
	Others	2	1.3
6	Experience		
	0-5 years	46	30.3
	6-10 years	37	24.3
	10-15 years	26	17.1
	Over 15 years	43	28.3
7	Management Training		
	Ever	144	94.7
	Never	8	5.3
9	If Ever		
	Diploma	62	40.8
	Master of Educational Management/Master of Leadership	26	17.1
	IAB Twin Program	2	1.3
	School Management Course	38	25.0
	Others	24	15.8

Based on the aspect of gender, the findings of the study show that 117 (77%) of the respondents are male while 35 (23%) are female. If you look at the age aspect, a total of 72 (47.4%) of the respondents are aged between 46-50 years, followed by 39 (25.7%) aged between 51-55 years, 38 (25%) aged 41-45 years and 3 (2%) aged 56-60 years. Based on the type of school, the majority of the respondents work in national secondary schools, consisting of 132 (86.8%) followed by religious national secondary schools, religious secondary schools, vocational technical secondary schools, art schools and others. In terms of divisions, 46 (30.3%) are from Kuching followed by other divisions namely Samarahan, Sri Aman, Betong, Sarikei, Serian, Sibul, Bintulu, Miri, Limbang, Mukah and Kapit.

Based on the grade, the majority is from grade 52 which is a total of 84 people (55.3%) followed by grade DG54 which is a total of 59 people (38.8%), grade DG48 which is a total of 4 people (2.6%), and grade DG44 which is a total of 3 people (2.0%)). From the aspect of experience in management, the experience of 0 to 5 years is the highest, which is 46 people (30.3%), followed by more than 15 years, 43 people (28.3%), 6 to 10 years experience, 37 people (24.3%), and 10 to 15 year as many as 26 people (17.1%).

Based on the aspect of management training, the majority of principals have undergone management training which is 94.7 mean average representing 144 people. While principals who have never taken the course are 5.3 average mean score obtained representing 26 principals. Based on the type of training, the majority is from the NPQEL course which is as much as 40.8 minutes which is a total of 62 principals, followed by those who have attended the school management course which is an average of 25.0 minutes which represents a total of 38 principals.

b. Emotional Intelligence Profile by Gender

The Mann Whitney-U test is a non-parametric test that functions as an analyzer of the difference between two independent samples whose dependent variable is ordinal scale data (Chua Yan Piau 2008: 93). This section will discuss the use of Mann Whitney-U in testing whether there is a difference between the respondents of 152

principals. In this study, the Mann-Whitney-U test was performed to make a comparison between two gender groups, namely 117 male and 35 female groups. The test results found that gender is significantly related to emotional intelligence ($z = 0.043$, $p < .05$) and competence ($z = 0.025$, $p < .05$) but does not have a significant relationship with quality management ($z = 0.200$, $p > .05$). The results in Table 4.9 show that there is a difference in emotional intelligence and competence for gender, but there is no difference in quality management.

Table 2: Mann Whitney-U test for gender

Mann Whitney-U test for gender

a	Emotional intelligence	Quality management	Competence
Statistics test			
Mann-Whitney U			
Homogeneity	0.683	0.807	0.815
Z	0.043	0.200	0.025
Asymp. Sig. (2- Stained)			
a. Grouping Variable: Gender			

a. Profile of Emotional Intelligence, Quality Management, and Competence Based on Experience

The Kruskal Wallis-H test is a test used to obtain an analysis of the difference between more than two independent samples on the dependent variable (ordinal scale) as the function of the Mann-Whitney-U test. However, the Mann Whitney-U test is also used in this section as a follow-up test in identifying which pairs of categories form a significant difference overall (Chua 2008: 173). For this study, the Kruskal-Wallis test was performed to make comparisons based on age and experience.

b. Profile of Emotional Intelligence, Quality Management and Competence Based on Age

The test results in Table 3 show that different ages have a significant difference in terms of quality management ($\chi^2 = 10.072$, $p < .05$), but there is no significant

difference in emotional intelligence ($\chi^2 = 6.997, p > .05$), and competence ($\chi^2 = 3.571, p > .05$). This means that in this study, different ages have different levels in terms of quality management, but do not have different levels in terms of emotional intelligence and competence.

Table 3: Kruskal-Wallis Test for Age

Kruskal-Wallis Test for Age

a, b	emotional intelligence	quality management	competence
Statistics test			
Chi Squared	6,997	10,072	3.571
Df	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	0.072	0.018	0.312
a. Kruskal Wallis test			
b. Variable Group: age			

4.6.3 Emotional Intelligence Profile, Quality Management, And Competence Based on experience

The results of the test as in Table 4 show that the different experience periods for the chi square (5, N = 152) do not have a significant level of difference in terms of emotional intelligence ($\chi^2 = 3.957, p > .05$), quality management ($\chi^2 = 2.507, p > .05$), and leadership competence ($\chi^2 = 2.590, p > .05$). This means that in this study, different periods of experience do not have different levels of emotional intelligence, quality management and leadership competencies.

Table 4: Kruskal-Wallis test for experience

Kruskal-Wallis test for experience

	emotional intelligence	quality management	competence
Chi Squared	3.957	2.507	2,590
Df	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	0.266	0.474	0.459
a. Kruskal Wallis test			
b. Variable Group: experience			

E. DISCUSSION

When discussing emotional intelligence, demographic factors need to be taken into account because they are important factors to emotional intelligence including gender (Mayer, Caruso, & Salovey (1999); Calvallo & Brienza (2002); Rivera (2003); Imndell & Pherwani (2003).); Oshagbemi (2000)), age factor (Bar-On (2000); Click (2002)), and experience factor (Click (2002); Mustamin et al. (2013)). Among the issues that involve demographic factors include the issue of emotional intelligence which is said to be that emotional intelligence will increase in parallel with increasing age (Bar-On, 2000).

However, this is contrary to the study conducted by Cook (2006) who found that increasing age has no effect on emotional intelligence. In terms of gender, studies have shown that female administrators are better than men in terms of emotional intelligence (Calvallo and Brienza, 2002) and found that women obtain higher scores in the competencies of self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and social skills (Boyatzis and Sala, 2004).

The results of the study show that there is a difference in the level of emotional intelligence and competence based on the factors of gender, age and experience of school principals. This difference is in line with Rorlinda's (2009) study on school principals in Sabah. The results of the competency-related study are not in line with the findings of Suparno (2001) and Mohamad Sani (2007) who found that there is a significant difference between the competence of male and female principals.

From the results of this study, it can be concluded that the level of emotional intelligence does not correlate with age. This result differs from Noriah et al's (2003) study saying that age is a factor in increasing a person's emotional intelligence (Noriah et al). This result is also different from the study of Bar On (2000) who also found that emotional intelligence can increase in parallel with the increase of a person's age. This study is in line with Click's Study (2002) which found that the duration of experience does not affect a person's level of emotional intelligence. Nevertheless, Fernandez (2001) and Mustamin et al (2013) found that the duration of experience affects a person's level of emotional intelligence.

For quality management, the results of the study show that there is no difference in the level of quality management with the age factor, but there is a difference in the level of quality management for the factors of gender and experience. As for competence, the findings show that there is a difference in the level of competence for the three factors of gender, age and experience. For the analysis based on the construct, the findings of the study show the highest mean score on the self-awareness domain for the group of principals. This shows that the values of self-awareness are quite influential in improving the emotional intelligence of the principals concerned. The low mean score on the social skills domain, gives the implication that both groups of principals use less of their social skills in improving their emotional intelligence.

The findings of the study also show that there are differences in emotional intelligence profiles based on gender and age. However, the difference is very small. The findings of the study show that the two groups studied have almost similar profiles, that is they have high scores on the self-control domain and relatively low scores on the empathy domain. This shows that both groups are very concerned about control values and other things that can make them more mature, so that can make their emotions more stable.

Overall, the results of this study have successfully answered the research questions and also achieved the main objective of the study. Based on the results of the study, it has been formulated and carefully discussed and finally a number of recommendations and their implications have been presented to the parties involved. Researchers are of the opinion that the training program provided by the ministry to all school leaders is at an impressive level since the Malaysian Education Development Plan (2013-2025) was introduced.

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